

Supplementary Material for “Time-Respecting Paths in Letter Networks Reveal Opportunities for Influencing Information Transmission during the European Reformation”

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1 Letter Data

1.1 Digitising Flashcards from the Bullinger Letter Edition

Since Heinrich Bullinger’s letter edition had not been fully digitised at the time of data collection, I manually digitised the metadata for the missing letters. Each letter’s metadata was recorded on a physical flashcard. To extract the data, I used Python’s Tesseract library to perform optical character recognition (OCR) on scans of the flashcards. Figure 1 provides an example of such a flashcard. Each box corresponds to another metadata field (e.g., sender), and all flashcards comply with the same format of boxes.

Datum 1546 Okt. 1.	Absender Bullinger Heinrich Zürich	Empfänger Simler Peter Kappel
Autograph	Kopie	Photokopie ZB
Standort <i>Zürich 28</i>	Standort <i>22B, A: 567, 176</i>	Bull. Corr. 70 Bl. 1, S. 1
Sign. <i>1546.41</i>	Sign.	Abschrift ZB
Umfang	Umfang	Bull. Corr. 113 Bl. 1, S. 1
Sprache	Literatur	
Gedruckt		
Bemerkungen Incipit: Früntlicher, fürgeliepter herr und gevatter, Heinrychen, minen sun		

Figure 1: Flashcard of the Bullinger edition.

1.2 Data Model

The total letter data set includes 26,663 letters exchanged between 3,370 persons from the editions of the nine selected reformers. The data are stored in nine tables in a relational database (SQLite) (Fig. 2). The attributes of the tables are described below. The number in brackets indicates the percentages of missing entries relative to the total number of entries in the respective tables.

- **Letters**

- `letter id` (missing: 0%): Unique letter identifier. Maps to Letter Sender Map, Letter Receiver Map, and Letter Original Language Map to retrieve the sender(s), receiver(s), and language(s) of the letter.
- `sending location id` (missing: 18.88%): Unique identifier for sending location of letter. Maps to Locations table.
- `receiving location id` (missing: 42.71%): See above.
- `sending date` (missing: 0.39%): Day-specific sending date, result of disambiguation of `sending date original`.
- `sending date original` (missing: 35.11%): Sending date with ambiguities.
- `text` (missing: 87.55%): Letter text.
- `document url` (missing: 35.14%): Url to webpage where letter was crawled from.
- `print version` (missing: 83.46%): Publication of print letter edition.

- **Persons**

- `person id` (missing: 0%): Unique person identifier. Maps to Letter Sender Map, Letter Receiver Map to retrieve whether a person sent or received a specific letter.
- `first name` (missing: 18.45%): First name of the person.
- `last name` (missing: 1.73%): Last name of the person.
- `title` (missing: 76.42%): Political or professional title of person (e.g., duke, pastor).
- `gender` (missing: 8.07%): Gender of person (M: male, F: female).
- `dnb link` (missing: 88.63%): Description of person on website of German National Library.
- `indiv vs group` (missing: 1.70%): Indicates whether entry corresponds to an individual (1, e.g., Martin Luther) or to a group (0, e.g., the pastors of Strasbourg).
- `person vs institution` (missing: 1.70%): Indicates whether entry corresponds to a person (1, e.g., Martin Luther) or an institution (0, the university of Wittenberg).

- **Letter Sender Map**

- `id` (missing: 0%): Unique identifier of entry.
- `letter_id` (missing: 0%): Unique letter identifier. Maps to Letters and Letter Original Language Map to retrieve other attributes of a sender's letter.
- `sender_id` (missing: 0%): Unique identifier for senders of letters. Maps to Persons to retrieve other attributes of this sender.

- **Letter Receiver Map**

- `id` (missing: 0%): See above.
- `letter_id` (missing: 0%): See above.
- `receiver_id` (missing: 0%): See above.

- **Letter Original Language Map**

- `id` (missing: 0%): Unique identifier of entry.
- `letter_id` (missing: 0%): Unique letter identifier. Maps to Letter Sender Map and Letters to retrieve other attributes of this letter.
- `language_id` (missing: 71.39%): Unique language identifier. Maps to Languages to retrieve (one of) the language(s) of a letter.

- **Languages**

- `language_id` (missing: 0%): See above.
- `language` (missing: 0%): Name of the language.

- **Person Alias Map**

- `id` (missing: 0%): Unique identifier of entry.
- `person_id` (missing: 0%): Unique person identifier. Maps to persons to retrieve other attributes of that person.
- `alias_id` (missing: 0.74%): Unique alias identifier.

- **Aliases**

- `alias_id` (missing: 0%): Unique alias identifier.
- `alias` (missing: 0%): Alternative name of a person.

- **Locations**

- `location_id` (missing: 0%): Unique identifier of a location.
- `location` (missing: 0%): Name of location
- `longitude` (missing: 0.83%): Longitude of location.
- `latitude` (missing: 0.83%): Latitude of location.
- `geoname` (missing: 0.94%): Link to the geonames database.

Figure 2: Entity relationship diagram of the Reformation database. Boxes correspond to tables and entries to table columns. The connecting lines between boxes illustrate the mapping between tables in the crow foot notation. For example, since a person can have zero or several aliases, one entry in Persons maps to zero or many entries in Person Alias Map.

Figure 2 shows how the data tables are linked in an entity relationship diagram. The connecting lines between the tables indicate the type of mapping between entries and are written in Crow Foot notation. They are read from left to right and top to bottom. For example, the connection from Letter sender Map to Letters indicates that one letter can have zero or several senders. The connection from Persons to Person Alias Map indicates that one person can have zero or several aliases, such as Martin Luther being known as ‘brother Martin’, ‘Ludder’, or ‘Martin of the Wartburg’.

2 Data-Driven Estimation of Memory (δt) in Time-Respecting Paths

I present two exploratory data-driven approaches on how to estimate the upper bound of inter-edge times δt , corresponding to human memory. δt represents the maximum time allowed to pass between the sending dates of two consecutive letters in a time-respecting path. If the inter-edge time is larger than δt I assume that ideas from the first letter are forgotten and not passed on in the second letter: the path is broken. Otherwise, if the inter-edge time is smaller or equal to δt , I assume that ideas are passed on. My approaches use waiting times and temporal path entropy, respectively. As I will show, both approaches are currently unfeasible, and I eventually use a heuristic to choose $\delta t = 15$ days in the main analysis.

2.1 Waiting Time Approach

For the waiting time approach, I assume that characteristic values of travel and waiting times capture the maximum memory capacity of reformers and hence δt . I first estimate the reception dates of letters from the modern walking distance between the sending and receiving place using the GoogleMaps API (Google 2005)¹. From these reception dates, I infer travel and waiting times of the letters, compute their frequency distributions, and choose their means as characteristic values. I define δt as the sum of these mean travel and waiting times to indicate that the typical letter exchange passes on ideas.

The waiting time approach faces three main limitations. First, data requirements are substantial since reformers have to receive at least one letter before sending one, and sending and receiving places must be known for the letters. Due to these restrictions, I can only use 1% of reformers and 24% of edges in the data leading to non-representative travel and waiting times. Second, long travel times are disadvantaged because they are larger than the typical travel time. Third, long waiting times are disadvantaged since I assume that the waiting time only contributes to a fading memory.

¹Assuming that 16th-century travel routes are proxied by modern ones is reasonable, since modern travel routes often follow ancient ones.

Figure 3: Temporal path entropies of observed (■) and randomised (■) letter correspondence network. Computations are based on code by Petrović, Wegner and Scholtes (2023)

However, individuals may also use the waiting time to refresh their memory when they read the letter several times or discuss its content with others in personal conversations.

Results of the waiting time approach reveal a mean travel time of about a day (34.80 hours, $SD = 29.69$ hours) and a mean waiting time of 122 days ($SD = 473$ days) leading to $\delta t = 1 + 122 = 123$ days. This indicates that letters traveled fast but reformers waited for more than four months between receiving a letter and sending out a new one. At first sight, four months seem to be surprisingly long to remember an idea and to pass it on. However, it is more likely that 123 days do not reveal the relevant time scale since I used a very small sample (1% of reformers and 24% of edges) which biased the result. Four months is not representative for the true waiting time of reformers, and I therefore did not use the waiting time approach to compute δt .

2.2 Temporal Path Entropy Approach

The second approach infers δt from the entropy computed for the frequency distribution of path lengths. This measure, called temporal path entropy, checks whether paths of different lengths occur at the same frequency or are heterogeneous in their occurrence. The minimum entropy indicates the relevant δt because correlations between time-consecutive edges are maximised at the relevant time scale, i.e., they become most predictable and less uncertain, which decreases entropy (Petrović, Wegner and Scholtes 2023).

Figure 3 shows the resulting entropy values (y-axis) for different time scales up to 100 days (x-axis). No clear minimum can be observed indicating that the relevant time scale is not straightforward to extract from the data. Moreover, standard deviations for paths of lengths two, three, and six are large indicating that only a few paths of these lengths are available in the data. These results are likely caused by the omission of waiting times. The minimum entropy of one day is therefore an artifact of our choice to only use the sending dates of letters to define time-respecting paths. From a historical perspective, an inter-edge time of one day, i.e., the time between two sending dates, is far too short for the average letter in the Holy Roman Empire to travel to its recipient and for the recipient to write and send out a follow-up letter. Since temporal path entropy does not cope well with sparse data, I did not use it to infer δt in the main analysis.

3 Robustness Checks

I perform robustness checks to investigate to what extent the results depend on the specific choice of $\delta t = 15$. I investigate degree-corrected betweenness and degree-corrected closeness for $\delta t = 1, 2, \dots, 20, 30$ days, 3 months, 0.5 years, 1 year, 1.5 years, 2 years.

I divide δt into three ranges, small (1 – 7 days), medium (8 – 20 days), and large (< 30 days), because the ranks seemed to be more stable in these ranges compared to the full range.

Figure 4 shows the most frequently top-ranked reformers for each measure across different δt s. 'Top-ranked' means they appeared most often in the top 10 across all δt s. Results show that most reformers remain in the top 10 for 15-25% of the plotted δt s, indicating that these reformers tend to rank high in both betweenness and closeness across the tested δt s. However, the actual frequency scores of top 10 reformers vary a lot, exceptions include small δt -closeness (Fig. 4b), medium- δt closeness (Fig. 4d), and selected reformers for large δt closeness (Fig. 4f, Bombasius, Winkeli, von Dormheim, Alexandre).

These results suggest that although the exact scores and ranks vary with delta t, the group of top-ranked reformers stays fairly stable. This means the score differences are not large, increasing the likelihood that the k-means clusters remain similar in composition.

Figure 4: Effect of δt on most frequent top 10 ranked reformers for degree-corrected betweenness and degree-corrected closeness.

4 Permutation Tests

A permutation test assesses the significance of an observed effect by repeatedly shuffling the data and comparing the test statistic to the distribution of statistics from these shuffled datasets. In this analysis, I use a permutation test to determine the optimal number of clusters. The observed effect corresponds to the silhouette scores of a clustering solution for a specific number of clusters k . The permutation test determines how likely this silhouette score is to have occurred by chance.

For the permutation test, I compute a null-distribution of silhouette scores by running k-means clustering for a specific k on 1,000 randomised feature matrices where randomisation is achieved by shuffling the scores per feature. This procedure is repeated for all tested k , resulting in a null-distribution of silhouette scores per k .

Per k , the significance of the observed silhouette score is assessed by comparing it to its

corresponding null distribution. For this comparison, the p-value is computed which is the proportion of null values that are “more extreme” than the observed value. In this analysis “more extreme” means “larger” since larger silhouette scores represent a better clustering solution. If the p-value is smaller than a pre-determined threshold (α level), which conventionally is often set to 0.05, we reason that sufficient evidence is provided to claim that the observed silhouette score is unlikely to have resulted by chance. That is, if less than 5% of null silhouette scores are larger than the observed silhouette score, the corresponding number of clusters k for this solution is considered meaningful. We say that the effect, the number of clusters, is significant. If several k 's result in significant effects we choose the smallest k for k_{best} since, based on Occam's Razor, we prefer the least complex model.

Since I perform multiple significance tests, one for each tested k , there is a risk of multiple hypothesis testing. Specifically, the chance of obtaining a significant result by chance increases with the number of tests conducted. To address this, I use a Bonferroni correction, which adjusts the α level by dividing it by the number of tests performed $\frac{\alpha}{n_k}$.

Permutation tests are more robust for determining the optimal number of clusters compared to traditional methods like the “elbow method” (Vieira 2012; Björklund 2019). The elbow method plots test statistics, such as silhouette scores, against the number of clusters and suggests choosing the point where improvements level off. However, this approach does not account for the influence of chance, as high scores might occur randomly. Permutation tests address this by comparing observed statistics to those from randomised data, providing a more reliable assessment.

References

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